

Synthesis of phenylthallium(III) dichloride and diphenylthallium(III) chloride complexes with tetradentate Schiff base ligands : a photoelectron spectroscopic study

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In continuation of our study¹, we now report some tetradentate Schiff base complexes with phenylthallium(III) dichloride and diphenylthallium(III) chloride.

Results and Discussion

The elemental analyses of all the molecular adducts were found satisfactory. The molar conductances of all the complexes in acetone ($20\text{--}30 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) suggest their non-electrolytic nature².

IR spectra of all the adducts exhibited $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ band at $1620\text{--}1610 \text{cm}^{-1}$ which appeared at $1640\text{--}1650 \text{cm}^{-1}$ in the free ligands³. The lowering of this band in the complexes indicates the coordination of nitrogen atoms of azomethine groups to the thallium. The far-IR spectra exhibited bands at $600\text{--}250 \text{cm}^{-1}$ (Tl-C)⁴. In $\text{PhTlCl}_2\cdot\text{SB}$ and $\text{Ph}_2\text{TlCl}\cdot\text{SB}$ (where SB = SB₉ or SB₁₀), the presence of stretching⁵ and bending⁶ modes of the OH group in the spectra indicates no deprotonation of the ligand.

It was noticed during observation of Tl4f photoelectron peak that binding energy of Tl4f is more in starting material, i.e. PhTlCl_2 or Ph_2TlCl , than their molecular adducts (Figs. 1 and 2). This concludes that effective positive charge on thallium metal ion is decreased due to increasing electron density on thallium metal ion after coordination. It was further observed during the analyses of N1s photoelectron peak that all the Schiff base ligands show a single symmetrical peak, while molecular adducts of the type $\text{PhTlCl}_2\cdot\text{SB}$ and $\text{Ph}_2\text{TlCl}\cdot\text{SB}$ (SB = 18) show two equal intensity N1s photoelectron peaks, one at higher binding energy side and other at lower having same binding energy value as that in their Schiff base ligand. These observations suggest that in $\text{PhTlCl}_2\cdot\text{SB}$ and $\text{Ph}_2\text{TlCl}\cdot\text{SB}$ (SB = 1-8), only two nitrogen atoms of Schiff base are coordinated, and the remaining two uncoordinated. In case of $\text{PhTlCl}_2\cdot\text{SB}$

Fig. 1. Tl4f binding energy (eV) in PhTlCl_2 and $\text{PhTlCl}_2\cdot\text{SB}$ (SB = Schiff bases 1 to 10).

and $\text{Ph}_2\text{TlCl}\cdot\text{SB}$ (SB = 9-10) only one N1s photoelectron peak at higher binding energy side was observed. This concludes that both the nitrogen atoms of the Schiff base ligands are coordinated with central thallium ion⁷. Further, the analyses of O1s photoelectron peak in $\text{PhTlCl}_2\cdot\text{SB}$ and $\text{Ph}_2\text{TlCl}\cdot\text{SB}$ (SB = 9-10) have not shown higher binding energy value than their Schiff base ligands (Fig. 3). This observation concludes that oxygen atom of these Schiff base ligands are non-bonded with thallium metal ion. The binding energy of Cl2p photoelectron peak was observed at

Fig. 2. Tl4f binding energy (eV) in Ph_2TiCl and $\text{Ph}_2\text{TiCl.SB}$ (SB = Schiff bases 1 to 10).

~199.3 eV in all the molecular adducts, which suggests that in each complex the chloride ion is coordinated in the inner coordination sphere of the metal ion.

Fig. 3. O1s binding energy in $\text{PhTiCl}_2.\text{SB}$ and $\text{Ph}_2\text{TiCl.SB}$ (where SB = Schiff bases 9 and 10).

On the basis of the above discussion a trigonal bipyramidal (sp^3d hybridization) geometry is assigned for

the adducts.

Experimental

PhTiCl_2^8 and Ph_2TiCl^9 were synthesized and characterized by reported methods.

Schiff base ligands : A mixture of glyoxal/2,3-butanedione/1-phenylbutane-1,3-dione/acetylacetone/salicylaldehyde (2 mmol) methanol (50 ml) and *o*-phenylenediamine or ethylenediamine (2 mmol) (in case of salicylaldehyde 1 mmol of *o*-phen or en) was refluxed for ~3 h. TLC suggested complete conversion of ketone or aldehyde to the Schiff base. The solid product obtained after evaporation was air-dried and characterized by elemental analyses. The following ten such ligands (SB₁–SB₁₀) were prepared :

SB₁, bis(glyoxal-*o*-phenylenediamine); SB₂, bis-(glyoxal-ethylenediamine); SB₃, bis(2,3-butanedione)-*o*-phenylenediamine; SB₄, bis(2,3-butanedione)ethylenediamine; SB₅, bis(acac)-*o*-phenylenediamine; SB₆, bis(acac)-*o*-ethylenediamine; SB₇, bis(1-phenylbutane-1,3-dione)phenylenediamine; SB₈, bis(1-phenylbutane-1,3-dione)ethylenediamine; SB₉, bis(salicylaldehyde)-*o*-phenylenediamine; SB₁₀, bis(salicylaldehyde)ethylenediamine.

PhTiCl₂ and Ph₂TiCl tetradentate Schiff base complexes : A mixture of PhTiCl_2 or Ph_2TiCl (1 mmol) in dry CHCl_3 and the above tetradentate Schiff base ligand (1 mmol) was refluxed ~3 h. The solid product obtained after evaporation was air-dried.

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